

Cascadia Region Earthquake Science Center

2024-25 Seed Grant Program Final Report

Improving Offshore 3D Splay Fault Geometries and Slip Histories using Seismic Data Reprocessing and Structural Modeling

Anna M. Ledeczi, University of Washington, Seattle, WA
Nathan C. Miller, U.S. Geological Survey, Woods Hole, MA
Harold J. Tobin, University of Washington, Seattle, WA
Cailey B. Condit, University of Washington, Seattle, WA

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20512959>

U.S. National
Science Foundation

Improving Offshore 3D Splay Fault Geometries and Slip Histories using Seismic Data Reprocessing and Structural Modeling

Anna M. Ledeczi¹, Nathan C. Miller², Harold J. Tobin¹, Cailey B. Condit¹

¹ Department of Earth & Space Sciences, University of Washington, Seattle, WA

² U.S. Geological Survey, Woods Hole Coastal and Marine Science Center, Woods Hole, MA

The goal of this project as written in the CRESCENT seed grant proposal was as follows: 1) reprocess selected profiles along strike from 45° to 48°N from the CASIE21 crustal-scale seismic data to obtain higher-resolution and higher-quality imaging of the uppermost 1-2 km of the accretionary wedge; 2) convert high-resolution USGS sparker seismic data from the time to depth domain to constrain near-surface fault geometries; 3) use kinematic modeling in the MOVE software to derive individual fault slip rates and per-event-displacements; and 4) work with the CFM group to create updated 3D models of identified faults based on the new data sources.

At this stage, we have begun the reprocessing of the CASIE21 seismic reflection data (Carbotte et al., 2023). The time-migration reprocessing of the CASIE21 dataset has improved imaging of the near-surface structure by incorporating usable frequencies up to ~220 Hz, in contrast to the ~50 Hz maximum usable content in the currently available pre-stack depth migrated (PSDM) profiles (Fig. 1C). An example of the image quality gained through reprocessing is shown in Fig. 1, where the dominant wavelength of each reflector is reduced to ~10 m (Fig. 1B) from ~20 m in the existing PSDM product (Fig. 1A). The reprocessing work is still currently in progress. While the imaging in the shallow section has been much improved, reprocessing below the first multiple is still needed to create a seamless image from the plate boundary to the surface.

Figure 1. **A.** Depth to time conversion of CASIE21 line PD06B PSDM. This is the original profile as processed by ION Geophysical. **B.** Example of broadband reprocessing flow developed by Miller and Ledeczi on A. The near-surface resolution of the data has doubled. **C.** Power spectra of A and B.

In the meantime, we have been conducting growth strata analysis in the basins and sediments overlying the outer wedge to determine the relative sequence of fault activity. Work in Ledeczi et al. (2024) proposed that high wedge-top sedimentation in the Quaternary caused rapid outer wedge growth and deactivation of splay faults. Complementary work by Lucas et al. (2025) showed that for the margin offshore Washington, megasplay-like structures at the inner-outer wedge boundary do not exist or are buried by thick sediments. Preliminary work conducted on the reprocessed data confirms this model. In general, we observe that outer wedge faults exhibit in-sequence activity, with out-of-sequence activity on the megasplay continuing after the deactivation of nearby faults (Fig. 2B). The reprocessed, high-resolution near surface data allows us to make these observations directly (Fig. 2A), which were not supported by the original resolution of the CASIE21 data.

Figure 2. **A.** Reprocessed portion of CASIE21 PD07 with interpreted horizons and unconformity. **B.** Entire CASIE21 PD07 line showing relative activity of inactive outer wedge faults.

While slip rates for onshore faults are generally more available, offshore faults have highly unconstrained slip rates. This is a persistent issue discussed within the CFM working group of CRESCENT. The growth strata analysis shown in Fig. 2 has allowed us to assign relative ages to faults. The next steps for this project include using these fault geometries and in progress stratigraphic analysis (Shuck et al., 2023) to inform kinematic modeling using the MOVE software to further constrain total slip and slip rates for individual faults. This work has been presented at the American Geophysical Union 2025 Annual Meeting in New Orleans, LA (Ledeczi et al., 2025). In addition, this CRESCENT seed grant contributed substantially to a manuscript in preparation to be submitted to *Geochemistry, Geophysics, Geosystems*.

References

Carbotte, S. M., Han, S., Boston, B., & Canales, J. (2023). Processed pre-stack depth-migrated seismic reflection data from the 2021 CASIE21 multi-channel seismic survey (MGL2104) (Version 1) [Application/seismic-segy]. Interdisciplinary Earth Data Alliance (IEDA). <https://doi.org/10.26022/IEDA/331274>

Ledeczi, A., Lucas, M., Tobin, H., Watt, J., & Miller, N. (2024). Late Quaternary surface displacements on accretionary wedge splay faults in the Cascadia Subduction Zone: Implications for megathrust rupture. *Seismica*, 2(4). <https://doi.org/10.26443/seismica.v2i4.1158>

Ledeczi, A.M., Tobin, H.J., Miller, N.C., Lucas, M.C. (2025, December). Late Quaternary Evolution of the Cascadia Outer Wedge Constrained by Structural Modeling. In AGU Annual Meeting Abstracts (Vol. 2025, T016).

Lucas, M. C., Ledeczi, A. M., Tobin, H. J., Carbotte, S. M., Watt, J. T., Han, S., Boston, B., & Jiang, D. (2025). No evidence for an active margin-spanning megasplay fault at the Cascadia Subduction Zone. *Seismica*, 2(4). <https://doi.org/10.26443/seismica.v2i4.1477>

Shuck, B., Babendreier, C., Han, S., Carbotte, S. M., Beeson, J. W., Boston, B., Tobin, H.J. & Lee, M. (2023, December). A new regional stratigraphic framework for the Cascadia oceanic basin. In *AGU Fall Meeting Abstracts* (Vol. 2023, No. 197, pp. T53E-0197).